
A Study on Indian Rural Market & Its Emerging Trends

T.M.Chougule

M,com , Kset, B.Ed, Lecturer, Department of Commerce, D.M.S. Mandal's Bhaurao Kakatkar College,
Belgaum, Karnataka

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19847842>

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted: 02-04-2026

Published: 18-04-2026

Keywords:

Rural Marketing, present scenario, Challenges & strategies.

ABSTRACT

The competition level in market is increasing day by day. The companies in today's competitive market try their level best to mark their presence in the market. The companies are using differential marketing strategies and techniques to grasp the opportunities. Both urban & rural market have its own potential but with the global market penetration rural market is considered to be more potential market than the urban market recent studies has proved. The reasons behind this include growth of per capita income, increase in population and various governmental penetration schemes. The rural markets are growing faster than urban markets. To explore and understand rural market is important for any marketers today. Rural market is like goldmine but have lot of difficulties. The growth of rural market forcing the big companies to drove to rural markets. The paper focuses on emerging trends in rural market, challenges & strategies used to reach rural consumers.

INTRODUCTION:

In India the population range of rural areas is more as compare to urban areas, India's rural market covering nearly 70% of the population. As it covers large part of population, it contributes nearly half of the portion in India's GDP growth which led to significant increase in purchasing power of rural areas, which creates many opportunities for companies to increase their profit. Some recent data on the rural market in India shows that rural consumption in Q2 of 2023, rural volumes grew by 7.5%, the highest in eight quarters. This was accompanied by a 21% plus growth in modern trade. It also shows that Two-

wheeler sales, an indicator of rural consumption, showed signs of recovery in 2023. The rural FMCG market is estimated to cross US\$ 100 billion by 2025. Rural market is like a goldmine but tie up with many difficulties. To enter into rural market, marketer should be aware with all opportunities, challenges & the correct ways to handle the rural consumer, because of increased globalization the rural consumer behavior also changing from traditional concept to modern marketing. This needs to formulate a well-designed strategy to attract rural market. The rural marketers must think rural market for long-term success. The factors like internet connectivity, transportation facilities, increased per capita income, increased standard of living, ways towards digitalization, enable companies to serve the rural markets with full potentials to increase rural market growth.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM:

This proposed study is intended to know the recent trends in Rural Markets. The rural marketing gaining greater importance now a days because of its market share & increased contribution towards GDP. It's essential for the marketers to aware regarding changes happening in the Rural Market, to grasp the opportunities.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

1. To understand the needs for rural marketing.
2. To study the recent trends in Indian Rural Markets.
3. To study the challenges & strategies of Rural Markets.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The present paper is analytical study on emerging trends in Indian rural markets. Which focuses on how the Indian rural markets are rapidly evolving, needs properly understanding of rural market scenario, recent trends taken place & different strategies to be followed to deal with Indian rural marketing.

PRESENT SCANARIO OF RURAL MARKETING:

India's rural population comprises over 70% of the country's total population, representing a massive market growth with untapped potential. As of 2019, India consists of 664,369 villages. This is an increase from the 649,481 villages recorded in the 2011 census and the 638,365 villages recorded in the 2001 census. Around 908.8 million people in India lived in the rural areas in 2022, who contributes positively in Indian GDP. Rural Market provides many opportunities where companies with correct marketing strategies capture a big share in market. Rural retail market size valued at approximately US\$ 1 trillion,

contributes significantly to India's GDP. In 2021, the National Sample Survey Office (NSSO) reported that over 70% of rural households have seen an improvement in living standards in the last decade. According to reports rural markets are expected to contribute about \$100 billion in retail sales by 2025, presenting opportunities for growth.

Digital access in rural areas also surged in the past decade. India currently has close to a billion internet users, with 958 million active users. Of these, 548 million are from rural areas, as per the internet in India Report 2025. The widespread availability of low-cost mobile data has brought millions of rural consumers online. Several key players have shaped the rural ecosystem. Amazon, Flipkart, Meesho and snapdeal, along with home grown platforms, created diverse models to cater to India's rural markets. As e-commerce gains traction across India, it is reflecting a fundamental shift in consumer behavior; rural consumers are increasingly transitioning from traditional brick-and mortar shopping to online shopping. The arrival of e-commerce in India has been more than just a convenience for rural consumers; it has driven significant socioeconomic changes, empowering individuals, creating employment opportunities, and opening new markets for many small businesses and artisans.

NEEDS FOR RURAL MARKET:

There are many reasons that have driven the Indian companies to enter the rural India. Some of them are discussed below:

1. **Large, Diverse, and Scattered Rural Market, as it covers 70% of country's population.**
2. Traditional Perspective of rural communities provides demand pattern for specific brands.
3. The dependency on electronic media – film, radio, and television – is greater,
4. Development of infrastructure facilities such as construction of roads, Transportation, communication network, rural electrification and public service projects in rural India increased the scope of rural marketing.
5. Growth of rural FMCG increases. In the first quarter of 2024, rural consumption grew at a rate of 7.6% year-on-year (Y-o-Y), while urban consumption grew at 5.7%.
6. Favorable Government Policies to develop job opportunities and promote the sale of goods and services in rural markets.

7. Upgrading to technology and use of new modes of communication and media like mobile phones, television etc. creates enormous opportunities for business organizations.
8. Assistance from various Financial Institutions encourages the rural population for purchasing more goods by facilitating the loans and advances at an attractive rate of interests.

TRENDS IN RURAL MARKETING

The rural consumers are shifting towards sophisticated preferences. The focusable trends include:

- 1. Massive population:** India's rural population comprises over 70% of the country's total population, representing a massive market growth with untapped potential. Indian rural market is huge in size. The rural market is currently worth approximately 50% of the total volume for many FMCG categories, with contribution overall \$250+ billion Indian FMCG market. Because of large market size the opportunities for marketer increases.
- 2. Increased Smart phones penetrating:** The usage of smart phones in rural India increasing rapidly. Nearly 38 per cent of rural population using smart phones, which is about total 320 million peoples, is rural mobile phone users. Growing demand for smart phones creates demand for digital marketing. Increased smart phones helps to increase the demand for product, as people get familiar with product with the help media exposure.
- 3. Increased level of education & employment level:** In recent era, the people of rural India are giving equal importance to education. The rural people are aware of products through education and media exposure. The online shopping with the popular applications makes easy, as they providing demos and starts providing information through local languages. As the marketers enters in rural India the employment opportunities also generating.
- 4. Trend towards branded products:** By increasing access towards information and exposure towards advertising products by using social media applications, rural consumers are becoming brand conscious. Before purchase they are focusing now on quality, brand and durability of product. This trend has been encouraged marketer to provide a platform to offer branded products often unavailable in local markets.
- 5. Shift towards digital payments:** Cash on Delivery (COD) remains common and most trusted option but now rural customer's shows a clear shift toward digital payments. The benefits from

digital payments like Easy procedures, Convenience & Security level shifting consumer's attitude towards cash on delivery. The availability of these payment options creates consumer confidence, allowing them to make transactions easily without any issues.

6. **High customer service expectations:** As rural consumers moving towards online shopping the expectations towards after sale services also increases. Rural peoples also shifting towards leisure. They prefer online shopping to get product easily at their places without physical visit in the market. This demand has led companies to invest in localized after sales services given to rural customers to create customer trust and encouraging repeat purchases.
7. **Socially informed buying choices:** Social media platforms like facebook, instagram, & whatsapp are popular sources of product information and demonstrations, allowing consumers to carefully consider their options before making a purchase. This trend indicates a shift towards informed purchasing behavior. Marketer should be always active in social media exposures to gives many buying choices to consumers.
8. **Increased purchasing power:** Rural purchasing power has grown faster in the recent years. The factors like disposable income, Government initiatives and schemes and favorable demographics supporting Economic growth plays important role. The Government spending in rural India are increasing trends as compared to last years. Many schemes of government resulted in changes in people's habits and social life.

CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES IN RURAL MARKET:

Delivering to the rural markets is not an easy task of marketing; it is a real challenge to many marketers. The whole dynamics of rural markets are so unique that one has to look at beyond traditional marketing mix. The Culture is not similar to urban areas. The buying behavior is totally different adding emotional touch in every step of buying. Most of the marketer assumes the same marketing strategies applicable, which are applied in urban market. This misconception fails marketers' to penetrate over rural market. Marketer has to update with advanced mix containing the 4A's instead of the traditional 4P's of marketing. The first one Acceptability develop what the consumer wants, second stands for Affordability Make an affordable product, the third one is Availability product made available at villages and lastly Awareness - Don't promote the brand, demonstrate the product. Some other Strategies are being followed by companies in Indian Rural Markets are the salesman in rural markets should be trained well & should have command on languages followed in rural areas. The Companies

should concentrate on changing attitude of rural consumers; concentration should be given on changing needs. Companies should follow new technology to communicating its products and services to their customer.

CONCLUSION:

India's rural market providing many more opportunities which could have been extends to greatest, if Indian policymakers have made adequate facilities for rural India. In recent years India has witnessed a transformative shift towards online or digitalized shopping areas. The spread of affordable smartphones, increased internet penetration and supportive government policies have collectively speed up the adoption of online shopping across the nation. This creates enormous opportunities. There are several difficulties resisting the effort to fully explore rural markets. Successful rural marketing urge for a review of rural consumer profile, marketing atmosphere, developing proper understanding of the nature, designing the right products to attract them, and adopting media exposure for product as well as other appropriate strategies.

REFERENCES:

- <http://www.ibef.org/industry/indian-rural-market>
- Pavitra D Patil, 'Emerging Trends in Rural Marketing and Strategies', Online International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, {Bi-Monthly}, ISSN 2249-9598, Volume-07, Nov 2017 Special Issue.
- Dr. Ravita Jain, 'Market Literacy & Trend Analysis of Emerging Rural Market', International Journal of Business and Management Invention (IJBMI) ISSN (Online): 2319 – 8028, ISSN (Print): 2319 – 801X www.ijbmi.org || Volume 13 Issue 1 || January 2024
- Dr.Devarajappa.SN., 'A study on the recent trends in Rural marketing in India',Journal of Emerging Technologies innovative Research(JETRI), Volume 12, Issue 9, ISSN 2349-5162.
- B.Nandini, 'Emerging Trends In Rural Marketing To Become An Real Marketing',Anveshana's International Journal Research in Regional studies, Law, social science, Journalism & Management, Volume 1, Issue 4, ISSN : 2455-6602
- Satnam Singh, 'Study of Recent Trends in Rural Marketing', Vol-4 Issue-1 2018, ISSN (O)-2395-4396.